

Aurora-Fuzzware: Bridging the Gap to Enable Practical Fuzzing of Microcontroller-Based IoT Devices

Noah Holmdin^{1,2}[0009-0007-9085-5174]✉,
Ravishankar Borgaonkar¹[0000-0003-2874-3650], Egil Wille³[0009-0004-0113-8594],
and Martin Gilje Jaatun¹[0000-0001-7127-6694]

¹ SINTEF Digital, Trondheim, Norway
{ravi.borgaonkar, martin.g.jaatun}@sintef.no

² IIK, NTNU, Gjøvik, Norway
noahh@stud.ntnu.no

³ SINTEF Nordvest, Ålesund, Norway

Abstract. Firmware fuzzing has shown to be a useful tool to discover vulnerabilities in embedded devices. However, applying fuzzing effectively to real firmware — such as that used in wireless medical sensors and patient monitoring equipment — requires expertise and careful configuration. In this paper we present Aurora-Fuzzware, a workflow and configuration tool. It enables automatic configuration for the Fuzzware framework for Nordic nRF52-family of devices, and a structured approach for setting up a fuzzing process. We validated our approach through three 24 hour fuzzing experiments with different configurations, and through a questionnaire to one of our industry partners. The results show that (i) the configuration tool successfully generates working configurations for nRF52 binaries developed with the NSDK 15.3, (ii) workflow-guided optimizations identified through Aurora-Fuzzware significantly improved coverage, and (iii) while the configuration tool is relatively user-friendly, there remains clear room for improvement. To bridge the gap between academic prototypes and practical industrial use, future work should emphasize improving the usability and user experience of fuzzing frameworks.

Keywords: Medical devices · Security by design · Fuzzing · Testing · Fuzzware

1 Introduction

The proliferation of microcontroller-based embedded systems has created an expansive attack surface that remains inadequately addressed by conventional security testing methodologies. Microcontroller units (MCUs) are embedded in millions of IoT devices and critical systems, powering infrastructure spanning low-cost medical devices, automotive systems, smart home technologies, and industrial automation platforms. In the healthcare sector, MCU serve as the

backbone of patient monitors, wearable medical sensors, and wireless peripherals. Many of these systems rely on Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) communication, and execute firmware on ARM Cortex-M microcontrollers. As a result, vulnerabilities in this firmware could have direct impact on the safety of patients.

The ARM Cortex-M architecture, particularly prevalent in these applications, like all other MCUs presents unique challenges for security analysis due to its resource-constrained environment, real-time operating constraints, and hardware-specific implementation details.

Fuzzware [7] represents a significant advancement in addressing these challenges, providing a framework for coverage-guided fuzzing of ARM Cortex-M firmware through emulation-based execution. By abstracting hardware dependencies and enabling systematic Memory-Mapped Input/Output (MMIO) generation, Fuzzware demonstrates the potential for bringing established fuzzing methodologies to embedded platforms. However, despite its theoretical promise, the framework faces practical limitations that constrain its real-world applicability - including for healthcare manufacturers.

The current state of the Fuzzware [7] tool presents two critical gaps that currently limit the use of Fuzzware in practical security assessment. First, although Fuzzware is technically capable of emulating firmware for MCU families such as Nordic Semiconductor’s nRF52 series - one of the most common BLE platforms in contemporary IoT and healthcare devices — it does not provide automated or user-friendly mechanisms for generating working configurations for these platforms. Creating a functional configuration for nRF52 firmware requires deep familiarity with memory maps, interrupt structures, and peripheral behaviour. Second, while Fuzzware’s documentation is sufficient for simple demonstration targets, it does not offer the level of detail needed to guide users through the configuration of production-grade firmware. As a result, applying Fuzzware to Nordic MCUs remains error-prone, time-consuming, and largely inaccessible to developers who lack specialized fuzzing expertise.

In this paper, we address these fundamental gaps through a systematic investigation of enabling Fuzzware’s capabilities to practical embedded system security testing. We present a usability focused extension of the Fuzzware framework for the Nordic nRF52 family of platforms, which we call *Aurora-Fuzzware*. We focus specifically on Nordic Semiconductor’s nRF52, a representative target that combines widespread industrial deployment with sufficient complexity to validate our methodological approach. The nRF52’s integration of ARM Cortex-M4 architecture, comprehensive peripheral subsystems, and sophisticated Bluetooth Low Energy stack presents challenges representative of contemporary embedded systems while providing concrete validation opportunities through industry collaboration.

This work makes the following specific contributions to the field of MCU-based embedded system security testing:

- **Aurora-Fuzzware:** We develop and validate *Aurora-Fuzzware*, a systematic usability-focused extension for the Fuzzware framework for Nordic nRF52 family of microcontrollers. This includes (i) an automated configuration gen-

eration script for nRF52 binaries, and (ii) a structured fuzzing workflow to guide iterative optimization.

- **Performance Optimization Framework:** We introduce systematic optimizations that significantly reduce fuzzing execution latency, eliminate configuration-related errors, and enhance overall testing throughput, validated through comprehensive performance benchmarking.
- **Industry Validation and Deployment:** We validate our approach through direct collaboration with IoT device manufacturers, demonstrating practical applicability beyond controlled research environments.
- **Practical Guidelines for Using Fuzzware on Real Firmware:** Based on our findings, we provide guidelines that bridge the gap between academic fuzzing tools and real-world embedded system security assessment, providing actionable guidance for researchers and practitioners.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: We present relevant background material in Section 2. Then, Section 3 features the methodology used for evaluating our approach. Section 4 introduces the design for Aurora-Fuzzware including a configuration tool introduced in Subsection 4.1, and a iterative workflow introduced in Subsection 4.2. Section 5 includes an evaluation of our framework. The results are then discussed in Section 6, including suggestions for future work and limitation with our approach, Section 7 concludes the paper.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Fuzzing MCU based IoT Devices

Fuzzing is a security testing technique that was first properly described by Bart Miller and colleagues more than 35 years ago [5]. When testing the robustness and security of embedded device firmware, fuzz testing has proven to be an effective and useful tool for identifying security vulnerabilities and other weaknesses [7, 8]. There are various fuzzing frameworks available, both open-source and paid services.

The context of this study is embedded medical devices, with the main focus on fuzzing of Arm Cortex-M devices using open-source tools. In previous work [10] we have studied which fuzzers could be suitable for fuzzing of such embedded firmware, and here we concluded that the Fuzzware fuzzer [7] was the most suitable for our purposes.

Fuzzware is an open-source fuzzing framework that can be used to inject unexpected MMIO reads in an emulated environment of embedded devices. While it has shown to be effective in identifying zero days, it is also noted to be difficult to configure for testing SoC's, and often requires hours/days of trial and error before finding a configuration that works for their target. This challenge is not unique for fuzzware, but rather a consequence of the numerous embedded architectures and peripherals, which have led to a plethora of tools and an overall lack of generic solutions for embedded fuzzing [3].

2.2 Challenges with Fuzzware

In their thesis, Sørlien and Solnør [9] conducted experiments with Fuzzware to evaluate its usefulness and whether it could be used to identify vulnerabilities. Their results highlight the limitations of Fuzzware from a practicality context.

Initially, they created configuration for a nRF52 binary through Fuzzware’s automatic configuration tool, which could not generate a working memory map for the binary. Then, they collaborated with their industry partners to create manual configurations, yet encountered several issues. This highlighted that even with assistance from maintainers of the firmware, configuring the fuzzer is not straightforward.

One of the created configuration could successfully be emulated, but led to a high number of false positive crashes. They note that understanding the output of the fuzzer was time consuming, and they could eventually conclude that the crashes occurred because the emulator was emulating the firmware’s elf file instead of the binary, which Fuzzware does not support. They note that the documentation regarding the use of elf files was ambiguous, and that the documentation is general is not sufficient for easily setting up a fuzzing process.

They conclude with stating that embedded fuzzing is currently infeasible for developers to use due the error-prone manual effort required, and calls for future work to improve their ease-of-use, to bridge the gap between fuzzers in an academic setting, and in an industry setting.

2.3 Requirements for a fuzzing tool

The usecase we are looking at involves fuzzing embedded medical devices which utilize a specific microcontroller, and based on this a set of requirements have been established [4]:

- R7.1: Cortex-M CPU support.** The tool shall have support for Cortex-M CPU.
- R7.2: Detection of common embedded firmware vulnerabilities.** The tool shall detect common types of embedded firmware vulnerabilities.
- R7.3: Consistent output for given input sets.** The tool shall, for a given set of inputs, provide identical output every time it is run.
- R7.4: Vulnerability location identification in source code.** The tool shall provide the necessary information to find the location of vulnerabilities in the source code.
- R7.5: Modelling interrupts.** The tool shall be able to model interrupts.
- R7.6: Script-executable tool functionality.** The tool shall be executable by scripts.
- R7.7: Bluetooth stack testing support.** The tool shall have support for testing the Bluetooth stack and firmware implementing the Bluetooth stack.
- R7.8: User friendly interface.** Users should be able to set up and use the tool, without needing assistance or clarifications from the tool developers.
- R7.9: Logging results in a parsable file format.** The tool shall log results to a file in a format that can be parsed.

- R7.10: Targeted testing with specific input sets.** The tool shall allow for targeted testing with specific sets of input.
- R7.11: USB interface testing support.** The tool shall have support for testing USB interfaces.
- R7.12: User-expandable functionality support.** The tool shall allow users to expand on the functionality

3 Methodology

To evaluate our framework, we conducted two type of assessments: one with benchmarking, and one questionnaire.

3.1 Benchmarking

The first involved a benchmarking experiment with three different Fuzzware configurations, with different level of optimizations identified through our framework. The specific optimizations are introduced in Section 5. In the experiments, we targeted a nRF52 binary file developed with the *Nordic Software Development Kit* (NSDK), provided by an industry partner. We ran Fuzzware with 4 cores on a 2.90GHz Intel Xeon W-2102 CPU, in a timespan of 24 hours. The three sessions ran independently and sequentially.

To asses the performance, we developed a script that parsed coverage information from Fuzzware’s `pipeline.log`. After each session, the script retrieved the number of *unique translation block covered*, and the timestamp at which that number of translation blocks was reached. A translation block represents a a set of CPU instructions, that the emulator treats as a single block. The total coverage is therefore measured as a the number of unique translations block reached within the runtime of the experiment. The script then output a line chart of the coverage from all log files provided as input, where the x-axis shows timespan and 0 represents the start of the experiment, and the y-axis shows the unique translation blocks covered.

The goal of the benchmarking experiment was (i) to evaluate whether the framework could generate a functional Fuzzware configuration for the target firmware, and (ii) to determine whether our optimization approach resulted in improved coverage compared to the baseline configuration.

3.2 Industrial Questionnaire

We selected industry partners based on their active nRF52840 development and willingness to integrate experimental security testing tools.

To assess the user-friendliness of our framework, we provided one of our industry partners with a SUS [2] questionnaire regarding their user experience of using the configuration tool. The questionnaire consisted of 10 ordinal (Likert-scale) questions regarding various aspects of usability.

The goal of this assessment was to evaluate whether practitioners found the framework to be user-friendly.

4 AuroraFuzz Fuzzing Framework

The Aurora-Fuzzware Framework provides a practical approach for setting up a fuzzing process for the nRF52 family of devices. It consists of an automatic configuration tool, and a work flow for continuously improving the performance of the fuzzer. In this context, performance indicates the amount of translation blocks the fuzzer reaches, within an amount of time.

4.1 Configuration Script

The configuration script is a command line script created with Python. It enables simple generation and modification of a Fuzzware configuration file. The script takes the relative path of the target directory (the folder containing the binary file), and the name of the binary file as arguments. Upon execution, it loads a pre-defined memory map template suitable for devices in the nRF52 family. The script enables users to modify and test the emulation configuration directly from the command line. For example, users can:

- Create static binaries of UICR and FICR memory sections, directly from a USB connected board.
- Add bootloader filtering that sets certain MMIO reads in boot loader as static (for firmware developed with Nordic SDK 15.3).
- Add, remove, or modify fuzzware configuration models. These include boot requirements, MMIO models, interrupt model, and more.
- Start fuzzing sessions directly from script.

Figure 1 contains a flowchart of the script.

When the user prompts to save the configuration, a `.yaml` file is created and stored in the target directory. The file will then automatically be utilized when the user uses Fuzzware command line utilities. Additionally, there are three optional arguments that the user can utilize for further simplicity and optimization:

- `--run`: The run flag automatically initiates a fuzzing session, with an existing configuration.
- `--auto`: The auto flag is used to skip the configuration tool menu, and instead simply generates, and stores a configuration file in the target directory.
- `--elf {path}`: The elf flag gives the option of loading function symbols from an elf file. Additionally, this features performs automatic optimizations for the configuration.

The main contribution of the configuration script is a simple approach for creating Fuzzware configurations for nRF52 devices. However, this does not guarantee that the fuzzer will reach good coverage. Fuzzing is an iterative process that involves executing tests, analyzing results, and continuously refining the setup to improve coverage. The Aurora-Fuzzware approach for optimizing the fuzzing workflow is covered in the following section.

Fig. 1. The Aurora-Fuzzware Configuration Script

4.2 Optimization of Fuzzing Workflow

The Aurora-Fuzzware Framework proposes utilizing a structured workflow for implementing and improving a fuzzing process. The workflow is inspired by the *Plan-Do-Check-Act* (PDCA) cycle [1], which is commonly used in engineering processes for continuous improvement. The phases of the Aurora-Fuzzware workflow are defined as Objective Forming, Configure, Fuzz, Assess, and Optimize (see Fig. 2). The underlying principle of the workflow is that each fuzzing sessions produces signals (such as timeouts, hangs, stalls, etc.) that may reveal gaps, or issues with the configuration. These signals can be used to update the configuration, enabling more accurate emulation of the binary.

The initial stage of the workflow is to clearly define an objective for the fuzzing. Such an objective may involve reaching a target level of code cover-

Fig. 2. The Phases of the Aurora-Fuzzware

age, testing specific functionality of the firmware, or validating the behaviour of particular code paths. This provides a measurement to which the result of the fuzzing session can be assessed. We define reaching the target objective as achieving meaningful coverage.

Then, the configure phase involves creating an initial configuration for Fuzzing. For nRF52 binaries developed with the Nordic SDK, this can be automated through the configuration tool introduced in Section 4.1. Other approaches include creating manual configuration based on the device memory map, or using Fuzzware’s `genconfig` utility.

Once a configuration is created, the Fuzz phase involves running a fuzzing session. The session can be initiated either from the configuration script, or from manually using the Fuzzware `pipeline` utility. In early iterations of the workflow, it is advisable to set shorter run-time durations (e.g. one hour), as the set up may cause the fuzzer to get stuck in loops, or fail exploring meaningful code paths.

In later iterations the duration can be extended to twenty four hours. In our experience, an optimized configuration is likely to discover new code blocks past the 24 hour mark. However, at that stage it becomes important to consider the trade-off between computational resource usage (CPU load, energy consumption), and the marginal gains in coverage. Fuzzing is resource-intensive, often utilizing as much processing-power as possible.

Once the fuzzing session has concluded, the results should be assessed from three decision criteria. These include:

- Was the emulation successful?
- Did Fuzzware uncover crashes?
- Did the session reach meaningful result?

These can be answered through an initial evaluation of the `pipeline.log` which contains output data from Fuzzware. If the emulation is successful, it means that Fuzzware is able to emulate the binary with the created configuration. If

the session ends before reaching any code blocks, or with error messages relating to configuration issues, the results are not meaningful and the workflow should cycle back to the configure phase.

If the fuzzing session uncovered crashes, they should be analysed before moving to the next phase. This can for instance be done through the Fuzzware `replay` utility. If a crash is caused by issues with the configuration, it should be noted to be handled in the subsequent optimization phase. If the crash is rooted in a security weakness, it should be reported and handled appropriately.

Reaching meaningful coverage means that the fuzzer has successfully explored enough code to satisfy the objectives. If the target is reached, the fuzzing process can be paused until a new version of the binary is available for testing. Running more sessions with the same configuration would result in the same code paths, and the same potential crashes, therefore there is no point in cycling back to Fuzz phase before a new version is available.

If the fuzzer does not reach meaningful coverage, the results should be analysed from an optimization perspective. The goal is to find configuration gaps (e.g. code patches, boot requirements, static memory reads) that prevent the fuzzer from exploring deeper states. The Aurora-Fuzzware framework defines this as the optimization phase, which is only triggered once coverage stagnates, or when crashes indicate emulation issues.

Optimizations typically fall under two categories:

- **Execution-speed optimizations:** Techniques that reduce time spent in loops, delays, or uninteresting code paths in the context of the objective.
- **State-exploration optimizations:** Techniques that improve the emulators ability to reach deeper, previously inaccessible states.

For the nRF52 family, some optimization techniques are listed in Section 4.3. After optimizing, the workflow should cycle back to the Fuzz phase.

Once the fuzzer has reached meaningful it goes to the end state and remains idle until a new version of the binary should be tested. At that point, the processes should cycle back to the configuration phase.

An example of an automatic optimization created from the Aurora-Fuzzware workflow is seen in the configuration script's Executable and Linkable Format (ELF) argument. Once an ELF file is provided, the file's function and object symbols are retrieved. These are then traversed and matched with two patterns: one that multiple delay functions in the Nordic SDK 15.3 library follows, and one specifically for the `c` function `sprintf`. If either of these are found, a patch is inserted at their location in the binary file. The patch is an instructions that immediately returns the instruction pointer back to the location from which the function was called.

4.3 Improving Coverage and Decreasing False Positives

The following are some initial techniques for improving coverage and reducing false positive crashes that were utilized during our experiments:

- **Execution-speed optimizations:**
 - **Add a Boot Model:** When bootloaders are present, adding a boot model that symbolically marks a successful boot can help skip redundant bootloader execution in later fuzzing runs. Initially, it may be useful to fuzz the bootloader itself to discover any low-level issues. However, once its behaviour is understood or deemed out of scope, focus can shift to the main application. This can be achieved by setting the `main` function as the boot target and configuring the reset handler as a required visited address.
 - **Skip Delays:** Delay loops are generally unwanted as it can take up much execution time. We mainly relied on patching calls to delays with NOP instructions, which improved execution speed, and reduced false positive (caused by interrupts during delays) crashes significantly.
 - **Set Manual Interrupts:** Adding interrupt models on functions that are loops waiting for interrupt events can greatly improve execution speed. In our experiments, there were some cases in which the right interrupts never triggered, adding a manual interrupt model then serves as a state-exploration optimization.
- **State-exploration optimizations:**
 - **Avoid FPU instructions:** Fuzzware does not support FPU instructions such as `vpush`. It is therefore recommended to compile binaries using flags that avoids them. Or try to patch over calls to functions that use them.
 - **Force program flow past “wait-for-flag” loops:** Firmware tend to wait for hardware events by polling status flags. Since the emulator might not reproduce these hardware events, these loops can prevent deeper exploration. Setting static MMIO reads, or inserting patches may help get past such behaviour.

While patching is a powerful tool for improving coverage, it must be done with care to preserve correct control flow. For example, inserting a `bx 1r` patch in the middle of a function (before `pop`), can corrupt the stack and cause unintended behavior.

5 Results and Industry Feedback

This chapter includes an evaluation of the Aurora-Fuzzware framework.

5.1 Benchmarking Experiment

The benchmarking experiment was conducted using three different configurations:

- Config 1: Generated with the configuration tool using only a binary file.
- Config 2: Generated with the configuration tool using both a binary file and an ELF file. The inclusion of the ELF file made the configuration include the automatic optimization introduced in Section 4.2.

Fig. 3. Coverage over time for three Fuzzware configurations

- Config 3: Generated with the configuration tool using both a binary and an ELF file, as well as manual optimization identified through utilizing several iterations of the Aurora-Fuzzware workflow. The manual optimization included patches at locations in the code that included “wait-for-flag” conditions, which the emulator did not replicate.

Fig. 3 demonstrates the result of the benchmarking experiment. Config 1 identified 512 translation blocks almost instantly, but afterwards got no improvements. This was caused by delay loops used in the firmware causing timeouts. Config 2 had automatic patches for the loops that caused problems and returned immediately when entering the loop. This resulted in a significant increase in coverage. However, similarly, its gains in coverage halted quickly. Configuration 3 reached more translation blocks than both Config 1, and Config 2, with 4317 blocks discovered after 24 hours. However, it then plateaued similar to the others.

5.2 Industrial Questionnaire

One partner responded to our questionnaire, and their feedback revealed that the system was somewhat unnecessarily complex (4/5), that the system was neutrally easy to use (3/5), that they might need the support of a technical person to use the system (3/5). Furthermore, it revealed that the functions in the system were well integrated (4/5), and they would like to use the system frequently (4/5).

These results suggest that, while the system is functional, there remain several usability challenges that warrant further refinement.

6 Discussion

The result of the experiments showed that our configuration script is successfully capable of automatically generating a configuration for nRF52 binary developed with NSDK 15.3, unlike Fuzzware’s default configuration tool. It also showed that the automatic optimization integrated when generating with an elf file, improved coverage significantly for a 24 hour session.

Table 1. Comparison of Fuzzware and Aurora-Fuzzware capabilities based on the defined requirements.

Requirement	Fuzzware	Aurora-Fuzzware
Cortex-M CPU support	Yes	Yes
Detection of common embedded firmware vulnerabilities	Yes	Yes
Consistent output for given input sets	No, some variations noted	No, some variations noted
Vulnerability location identification in source code	Yes, with limitations	Yes, with limitations
Modelling interrupts	Yes	Yes
Script-executable tool functionality	Yes (CLI command based)	Yes (CLI script based)
Bluetooth stack testing support	Indirectly	Indirectly
User-friendly interface	No	Yes, with limitation
Logging results in parsable file format	Yes, with limitations	Yes, with limitations
Targeted testing with specific input sets	Yes, with strict limitations	Yes, with strict limitations
USB interface testing support	Indirectly	Indirectly
User-expandable functionality support	Yes	Yes

In the context of the requirements presented in Section 2.3, Fuzzware, and Aurora-Fuzzware meets the requirements demonstrated in Table 1.

Fuzzware is specifically developed for the *Cortex-M* instruction set. One limitation in this aspect is that Fuzzware can not emulate FPU instructions, due to the underlying unicorn emulator.

Fuzzware is capable of *identifying vulnerabilities in embedded firmware*, as shown in [7]. Furthermore, the *Vulnerabilities location in source code* can be identified through analysing the output files of the fuzzing session, it is however time consuming and requires technical expertise and knowledge of the firmware.

Fuzzware has command-line execution support, while Aurora-Fuzzware expands with a *script executable functionality*, as the configuration tool enables modification of configuration, and running the session directly from the script.

Fuzzware has indirect *Bluetooth stack testing support*, as Fuzzware manipulates MMIO-reads and embedded devices typically handle bluetooth operations through MMIO-registers. This implies that the tool can indirectly test the Bluetooth stack by interacting with these MMIO operations, but not at a protocol level. Similarly, Fuzzware has indirect *USB interface testing support* for the same reasons.

As the result of our questionnaire indicates, the Aurora-Fuzzware configuration tool is somewhat user-friendly, but with obvious room for improvement. The benchmarking experiment however showed that configuration tool was capable of automatically generating a working configuration, which is an improvement compared to the automatic configuration for stand-alone Fuzzware for nRF52 devices. This suggest meaningful potential for further research in user-friendly fuzzing.

The tool *logs the result in a parsable format* through `.log` files. These are technically parsable, as they follow a structured pattern. There is however room for improvement as it requires developing custom parsing scripts. As Fuzzware is open-source, and the Aurora-Fuzzware will be made open-source, they have *user-expandable functionality support*.

While Fuzzware supports *target testing with specific input sets*, these need to be established through setting static MMIO reads in the configuration file. As these reads are specified using hexadecimal values, the process can be difficult to interpret, and prone to errors.

Lastly, each fuzzing session should produce the *same output for a given configuration*, although some variation has been noted through our experiments.

In summary, Fuzzware meets most of the criteria established by the NEMECYS project [4], with limitations, while Aurora-Fuzzware improves the user experience.

6.1 Limitations

As the configuration script is centred on user-friendly fuzzing, some capabilities of Fuzzware were left out of scope. One of these functionalities is the ability to create custom hooks through python that the emulation can initiate at specified timings or locations.

For more information about such additions, see Fuzzware’s github page [6].

As Aurora-Fuzzware is mainly focused on the configuration and optimization phases, it does not provide a structured approach for analysing crashes. This is an important direction for future work, to further improve the practically and feasible of fuzzing in industry.

Furthermore, once the fuzzer reaches meaningful coverage for a binary, and a new version of the binary is to be tested, the workflow needs to cycle back to the configuration phase and generate a new configuration. This means that previous manual optimizations done at specific addresses in the memory layout are unlikely to work on the new version, as the as the code layout may have changed.

In the benchmarking experiment, all configurations stopped discovering new translation blocks fairly quickly. This is mostly due to the general difficulty of emulating embedded firmware. Such firmware depends heavily on interrupts, hardware events, timers, and peripheral behaviour that are not fully reproduced by the emulator. Since the emulator is not a one-to-one replica of the actual hardware, some operations simply cannot be executed the same way they would on the device. In our experiment, this led to a natural plateau: even though the optimizations improved coverage, the fuzzer eventually reached a point where it could not make further progress because the expected hardware interactions were missing.

Our SUS questionnaire had small sample size of 1 respondent. This limits the generalizability of the findings on usability, and the results should therefore be seen as indicative rather than conclusive.

6.2 Future work

Going forward, future work in user-friendly fuzzing should focus on automated crash analysis and further assistance in configuration.

An automated crash triage tool could be used to categorize whether crashes are caused by configuration errors, or potential vulnerabilities. Furthermore, it could be used for understanding specifically what functionality in the firmware caused the crashed, as well as the MMIO inputs that caused the execution path to reach the functionality. One promising direction would be exploring machine-learning-based classifiers to group crash types or assist in reasoning about likely root causes.

Furthermore, while our work helps bridge the gap between academic fuzzing tools and industrial use, there is still room for improving user-friendliness. One direction is to translate the raw session output from the log file into a more structured and easier-to-understand format. Another is to provide suggestions for configuration optimizations based on signals observed during fuzzing, such as repeated stalls or loops. Visual dashboards could also make it easier to assess the results of a session and understand where the fuzzer is making progress or getting stuck.

Lastly, a case-study on the Aurora-Fuzzware workflow could help evaluate whether it helps industry teams in integrating fuzzing into their vulnerability discovery toolbox. Research tools are often powerful, but their potential remains unused if practitioners do not know how to apply them. Improving user-friendliness and usability is therefore essential for ensuring that the advances in vulnerability discovery methods actually benefit the real-world industry settings.

7 Conclusion

In this paper we have shown how using Fuzzware for embedded medical devices can be simplified through our custom configuration script and workflow. While there is still a need for specialized competence and manual effort from firmware

engineers who want to fuzz their binaries, Aurora-Fuzzware makes the process more accessible by reducing the configuration complexity, improving usability, and enabling more meaningful result on real embedded firmware.

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